

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

This use case is under a [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) license.

Cite as: Silke Bellanger et al., Handling Personal Data in Research: Use Case on Data Processing by Third Parties, 11 March 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14849756>.

Data Processing by Third Parties

Use Case

The Institute of Sports Science is conducting interviews with senior citizens in local sports clubs. There will be fifty-five interviews in total, each two hours long. The interviews discuss the role and significance of sports in one's own social life, and they also contain biographical passages.

The transcription of the interviews will only be partially completed by the researchers themselves. Student research assistants from the institute will also be involved in transcribing them, and the majority of this work will be done at low cost by a transcription company.

The researchers are wondering whether it is legally permissible for third parties to process the data, under what circumstances, and who is considered a «third party» in the first place.

What counts as data processing?

In addition to transcribing the interviews, data processing also encompasses conducting the interviews, analyzing them, any media processing of the sound and images (editing etc.), and the storage and deletion of data. In other words, data processing encompasses everything that can be done with data.

Who is allowed to process data?

In the framework of research at a university, data may be processed by anyone who is authorized to do so on the basis of a law or, if applicable, by anyone who has obtained informed consent from the individuals concerned (the data subjects). In principle, data are processed by the research team itself, but they are also processed by other university employees who are not part of the research team (auxiliaries) and by third parties external to the university. The research team of the project is responsible for the actions performed by auxiliaries and third parties.

Who is considered a third party in data processing?

Third parties are all persons or legal entities who are not directly employed by the university and are instead called in for a limited job; that is, they process data on behalf of those responsible for processing the data. Third parties can include external transcription companies, market-research agencies, or cloud providers.

What agreements must be signed with third parties?

Data processing by third parties is known as commissioned data processing. This requires a contract for commissioned data processing in which the purpose of the data processing, the specific categories of data, the responsibilities, confidentiality, and so on are defined.

In the case of data processing by student research assistants at the same university, there is an employment relationship, so they qualify as so-called auxiliaries. In this case, a confidentiality agreement is sufficient. But it is still advisable in such cases to define all the details as precisely as possible.

In all these cases, the researchers and their university bear the responsibility for ensuring that the data are handled correctly.

What does that mean for this case?

The Institute of Sports Science signs a contract for commissioned data processing with the transcription company. The institute consults the university's legal services to prepare the contract.

The student research assistants and researchers have an employment relationship for the duration of the project, and all of them sign a confidentiality agreement before beginning with the transcriptions. The researchers first ask the HR department if a standard agreement is available. Since one is not, they formulate a confidentiality agreement in collaboration with legal services and the data-protection officer.